

UNDERSTANDING GOOD PRACTICE IN THE DIGITAL TRANSFER PROCESS BY CONNECTING WITH THE DIGITAL PRESERVATION COMMUNITY

Bryony Hooper - University of Sheffield (digitalpreservation@sheffield.ac.uk)
Jenny Mitcham - Digital Preservation Coalition (Jenny.Mitcham@dpconline.org)

What we did...

The University of Sheffield identified a number of challenges in how they managed the process of digital transfers and deposits to their Archives and sought input from the DPC community to find an answer to an important question...

what does good practice look like for the deposit or transfer process?

When the DPC put this question to the community there was global interest. Two focus groups were held in February 2025. A range of different organizations from across the world took part, including national bodies, specialist repositories and universities.

What they said...

Some selected insights from focus group attendees on their experiences with digital transfers

"We cannot assume that an agreement written for physical material would be sufficient for digital or hybrid collections"

"Donors may transfer material in file formats we cannot identify or which we do not have the tools to meaningfully access"

"We've found donors often get overwhelmed and concerned they are 'doing it wrong'. For this reason, we have found that detailed questions or surveys tend to put off the donors"

"So much is about relationships rather than the deposit process alone"

"Sometimes just getting your hands on the records is hard enough that the other best practices get a bit side-lined and you will just take what you can get"

"Depositors are not standard"

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Share and consult with the community to continue to evolve good practice and anticipate new developments

What does good practice look like?

Here are our top 10 recommendations for those wishing to apply good practice in the digital transfer process:

- 1 Prioritise the relationship between the Archive and the depositor - the value and impact of this relationship should not be underestimated
- 2 Develop internal guidance and checklists on having conversations with donors and depositors
- 3 Understand that there is a careful balance when receiving digital files from donors and depositors. You may have to approach certain transfers with the mindset "Ask for more...but accept what you get"
- 4 Ensure you have documentation (such as Transfer Agreements, Deed of Gift templates) that are relevant for digital records. Consider addendums or additional documents that specifically cover digital acquisitions
- 5 Consider including in your agreements permission to undertake actions that ensure on-going preservation and access to these records - aim to "future-proof" your agreement as much as possible
- 6 Recognise that there is unlikely to be a one-size-fits-all approach to managing digital transfers or deposits. Your organisational context and the donors you engage with will shape your processes
- 7 Work towards being able to demonstrate that the integrity of the digital content has been preserved throughout the deposit/transfer process and that you have adequate documentation, metadata and permissions to understand, preserve and provide access to the content
- 8 Accept that a level of flexibility may be required depending on the type of deposit and the donor you are working with
- 9 Allow your documentation and processes to evolve over time based on experience

With thanks to all DPC Members who attended our focus groups, provided feedback and shared documentation on their own deposit and transfer processes

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